

Lung cancer patient cases (diagnosis images and clinical data) for the testing of AI models

ID: 49f05d44-19c4-4678-aca4-15bc093daa00

URL: <https://chameleon-eu.i3m.upv.es/dataset-service/datasets/49f05d44-19c4-4678-aca4-15bc093daa00/details>

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 273

Subjects count: 273

Age range: Between 32 years and 88 years

Sex: Male, Female

Body part(s): CHEST, ABDOMEN, LUNG, NECK, BRAIN, HEAD, WHOLEBODY, THORAX / ABDOMEN, THORAX, TAP, SPINE, TC
TOTAL BODY, TDM THORAX / ABD, RACHIS, THORAX INJECTE, CRANE, Unknown

Modality: CT, PT